

Science technology & Digital finance

journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**MODERN PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF DEMOCRACY AND MORALITY IN UZBEKISTAN****¹Spanov Meiirkhan, ²Kamolov Dostonbek Rustam ugli**¹*M. Auezov South Kazakhstan University, Candidate of Philosophical Sciences, Associate Professor.*²*Trainee teacher of the Department of Social Sciences and physical culture of the Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.***СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПУТИ ИХ РЕШЕНИЯ В ОБЛАСТИ ДЕМОКРАТИИ И ПРАВСТВЕННОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ****¹Спанов Мейрхан, ²Камолов Достонбек Рустам угли**¹*Южно-Казахстанский университет имени М. Ауэзова, кандидат философских наук, доцент.*²*Преподаватель-стажер кафедры социальных наук и физической культуры Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека.***O'ZBEKISTONDA DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI****¹Spanov Meyrxon, ²Kamolov Dostonbek Rustam o'g'li**¹*M. Auezov nomidagi Janubiy Qozog'iston universiteti, falsafa fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.*²*Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali Ijtimoiy fanlar va jismoniy madaniyat kafedrasi stajyor o'qituvchisi.***abstract**

This article provides information on democracy and ethics and existing conditions that currently exist in Uzbek society. In addition, modern solutions to existing problems have been given.

аннотация

В этой статье представлена информация о демократии и морали, существующих в настоящее время в узбекском обществе, а также об условиях, в которых они существуют. Кроме того, были даны современные решения существующих проблем.

annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola hozirgi kunda o'zbek jamiyatida mavjud bo'lgan demokratiya va axloq hamda mavjud shart-sharoitlar haqida ma'lumotlar beradi.

Qolaversa, mavjud muammolarga zamonaviy yechimlar berilgan.

Keywords:

society, ethics, problems, solutions, environment.

Ключевые слова:

общество, мораль, проблемы, решения, окружающая среда.

Kalit so'zlar:

jamiyat, axloq, muammolar, yechimlar, muhit.

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Introduction

The 21st century is characterized by the transition from an epicenter economy and politics to spirituality, which determines the total existence of mankind to this day. Because spirituality has become a consensus that determines all parameters of people's existence. One of the indicators that determines the relevance of solving the problem of the moral and ethical environment in society is the modern global ethics and the analysis of national, moral and ethical values, their development and improvement at the crossroads of the world.

A comprehensive study of the content, problems, and conceptual solutions of the community's moral and ethical environment and the efficient use of them in national and spiritual development have theoretical and practical implications. I mean:

- scientifically studying the moral laws and principles of the moral and ethical environment of society and solving its problems;
- improving the constructive aspects of the moral and ethical environment of society, consistently analyzing moral and ethical aspects based on the characteristics of modern national development;
- strengthening people's spiritual cooperation in a moral and ethical environment, developing moral skills in an individual, educating him morally and morally, developing and strengthening his will, and bringing up a truthful and humanitarian person;
- to develop and regularly improve a healthy moral and ethical environment in society and to apply it to the continuous educational process, to deepen the national, socio-ethical ideas in the minds and hearts of our people, including young people, in accordance with a truly moral and ethical environment;
- to strengthen the mechanisms of inheritance of moral heritage, to develop practical measures to achieve the idol of faith;

Analysis and results

It is noteworthy that the democratic society being established in Uzbekistan and the system of factors it is based on are new, rich in certain experiences, and positive characteristics. Therefore, the people of Uzbekistan, of more than 130 nations and nations, live in family, kindness, and harmony. This prohibits the development of indicators of the current existing moral and ethical environment.

Mike Mezi, an American scientist and publicist, determines the stability of the society environment in the following ways:

- a) the absence of a subversive revolutionary spirit;
- b) lack of an internal violence factor;
- c) non-nonsense changes to the Constitution;

- g) lack of sharp resistance to the structure;
- d) institutional structure and lack of stability in government [1].

Mature spirituality is the second most important moral and ethical indicator of a democratic society in Uzbekistan. Nationalism is the basis for the survival of this indicator. Its main components are deep knowledge, a healthy worldview, good virtue, and a mature. Effective work is to pursue a well-defined and accurate career in our society today, to live in exchange for your hard work, to live as owners and to follow such principles as social justice, conscience, faith, obligation, and duty in the hierarchy.

In the democratic society that is being established in Uzbekistan, the moral and ethical environment is being improved through communication. The first is the factor of traditionalism and morality in the east, and the second is the modernity and sociality of the West. It is this paradigm of traditionalism and morality, modernity and socialism that determines the characteristics of implementing moral and ethical indicators. Targeting is an ideal issue. For the democratic environment enjoys the priority of freedom and individualism . But to ensure the survival and evolution of any society , it imposes its requirements, norms, and rules on such principles as freedom and individualism [2] .

Therefore , it is satisfying for the majority of the members of any other society to mature morally and morally . After all, the targeted implementation of indicators of the moral and ethical environment in Uzbekistan is determined by the following requirements: – young people make up about 61 percent of the population of our country; – the harmonious composition of traditionality and modernity, morality and sociality in society; – external and internal spiritual aggression must be eliminated; – society should be morally and morally developed on the basis of national ideology. These necessities prohibit the normal composition of such principles and values as equality, freedom, individuality in the moral and ethical environment of our society. Why? Because there is doubt about absolute equality, absolute freedom, unconventional individuality, strict traditionalism and irregular modernity [3].

It is noteworthy that in the context of a democratic society in Uzbekistan, subjects of the moral and ethical environment are five: family, preschool, place of study (types of education), workplaces, and neighborhoods. It is noteworthy that this environment is fundamentally different from that of other democratic societies . The main, moral and ethical indicators for these aspects are education, discipline, formation, development, correction, activation, orientation, order, discipline, and well-being. In these five environments, seventeen norms, quality, requirements, and foods will be achieved in society by implementing basic moral and ethical indicators. It

should be noted that implementing the main indicators of society's moral and ethical environment will have a specific characteristic. These include:

1. The stability of the moral and ethical environment in the family environment; to be responsible for the upbringing of family members; protecting the family from spiritual, moral and social aggression; improving family culture and a healthy lifestyle.

2. The main moral and ethical indicator in the educational environment is education. Strengthening the harmony of education and training to improve the efficiency of practical work in this environment; the formation of an individual morally and morally healthy; protecting the mind, worldliness, and morality of an individual from bedtime ideas, influences, and ills; preparing an individual for life and work ;

3. Development of a key moral and ethical indicator in the workplace environment, in which to ensure the morality and community of the labor force; directing members of the community to high goals; accustoming members of the community to adhere to independence, individuality and community harmony; strengthen social engagement in community members.

4. Organize a basic moral and ethical indicator in the neighborhood environment. According to him, it is necessary to ensure the moral and ethical first, unified and moderate nature of the neighborhood. To do this, protect the neighborhood from social and moral ills; assistance in solving moral and ethical problems in families, labor and educational communities; protection of healthy lifestyles; compile compliance with the diet of social justice, freedom and commitment. Thus , in implementing indicators of the moral and ethical environment in a democratic society, the needs, purposes, and realities of this society are primary. Indicators of the moral and ethical environment in the conditions of a democratic society of Uzbekistan perform several important functions. The main features of these functions are:

- harmonious development of national and universal moral values;
- to direct members of society to high goals and creative work;
- diagnosis and assessment of the moral and ethical level of society. These functions are performed in a real environment, and therefore the main moral and ethical indicators have two characteristics: consequence and duration. If indicators are maintained, they will have a permissiveness characteristic, such as training, formation, correction, etc., but rather, if indicators are displayed depending on the real situation, such as teaching, explaining, directing, etc.

Conclusion

Therefore, the most important issue in this case is the timely understanding and rational use of the necessary indicators. In this case, there are two ways below. The first is the development of positive foundations of the moral and ethical environment;

the second is to fight the negative ills that affect the moral and ethical environment. These two paths bear fruit when applied depending on the situation.

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